

Spatial analysis of the combined sewer overflow durations in England and Wales

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Highlights

- Spatial distribution of CSO durations across England and Wales are highly unlikely to be random.
- Spatial clusters and outliers of CSO spill durations have been identified in England and Wales.
- CSO spill durations are correlated to regional climate and topography.

Introduction

Combined Sewer Overflows (CSOs) occur when the capacity of a combined sewer system is exceeded, resulting in the discharge of untreated wastewater diluted in stormwater into natural water bodies. These discharges act as a relief mechanism for the sewer system, mitigating flood risk, but at the cost of releasing pollutants to the environment. Discharges from CSOs are increasingly becoming a reputational concern for water companies in the UK. Richard Benyon MP (Benyon, 2013) instructed water company chief executives to monitor most of their CSOs by 2020 through the installation of Event Duration Monitoring (EDM). By 2022, English sewerage companies equipped 13,323 CSO sites with monitors, covering 91% of known storm overflows (EA, 2023a).

The EDM dataset can provide a high-level indication of where sewer systems are most overloaded. However, despite the abundance of data, we find ourselves in a "data-rich" but "information-poor" situation. To effectively shape policies and strategies, it is essential to convert this extensive data into actionable information. In this context, this research employs spatial analysis techniques, such as Global Spatial Autocorrelation and Local Indicators of Spatial Association (LISA) analysis, to reveal spatial trends and anomalies in the EDM data for the year 2022. This dataset, being the most current and encompassing the broadest coverage of CSO assets, offered a comprehensive basis for our analysis.

In this study, we specifically examine the average annual spill durations of CSOs across Local Authority Districts (LADs) in England and Wales. LADs serve as administrative units in the UK, and previous research (Mullin et al., 2018) has highlighted environmental inequalities across these districts. The objectives of our research are to investigate the spatial distribution of CSO spill durations within these LADs and explore potential correlation between these durations and climatic and geographic variables. Through this statistical and spatial analysis, we aim to identify possible disparities in urban water infrastructure management across these districts, with the ultimate aim of contributing to more equitable and effective environmental policies and strategies.

Methodology

Event Duration Monitoring (EDM) dataset

This research analyses the 2022 EDM dataset collected by water and sewerage companies in England and Wales. The EDM dataset relies on water level sensors strategically placed within discharge structures, such as weirs, to detect CSO spills. Based on the water level data and weir levels, CSO spill durations are calculated. The dataset records spill duration of individual CSOs on an annual basis, aggregating duration of multiple discharge events over the year.

The Rivers Trust (2023) has processed the EDM dataset by showing it in a “Sewage Map”, providing a spatial representation of sewer overflows. Researchers can download and analyse this data using GIS software. While acknowledging the potential presence of both systematic and random errors within the dataset provided by Rivers Trust, this study did not perform data validation due to the unavailability of water level data or CSO asset records.

Spatial Analysis

Average CSO spill durations within the LADs are computed by dividing the aggregated total durations with the number of CSO assets in the analysed LAD. Subsequently, using ArcGIS Pro version 3.1.3, we conducted both global and local spatial analyses based on this aggregated data. To define suitable neighbourhoods for LADs, we employed the Fixed Distance Band method, which assigns equal spatial weights to features within a specified distance from each other. In our research, this distance was measured using the Euclidean method. Additionally, we applied row standardization to create proportional spatial weights, a recommended approach to mitigate bias resulting from the imposed aggregation scheme (ESRI, 2023a).

The Spatial Autocorrelation tool was deployed to evaluate spatial structure. This tool computes the Global Moran’s I statistic and a single z-score value, indicating the extent of clustering or dispersion of the entire study area (ESRI, 2023b). To determine the fixed distance band that best reflected localized patterns of spill durations, we applied this tool across various fixed distance band values.

In order to identify local dependencies, we conducted LISA analysis using the Cluster and Outlier Analysis tool in ArcGIS Pro. This tool operates similarly to Hotspot Analysis, as it can identify spatial clusters of short (cold spots) and long (hot spots) CSO spill durations. However, it also evaluates each individual LAD influence on the global statistics, enabling the identification of statistically significant spatial outliers. Using Local Moran’s I statistics, the tool classifies LADs into categories like high-high, low-low, high-low outliers, and low-high outliers (ESRI, 2023c). To reduce the likelihood of false positives in cluster or outlier detection, we applied the False Discovery Rate (FDR) correction (Castro et al., 2006).

Having identified spatial patterns within the 2022 EDM dataset, our study aimed to explore the potential factors influencing the observed CSO spill patterns. For this purpose, we assessed the impact of rainfall by utilizing the HadUK-Gridded Climate Observations dataset (MetOffice, 2023) for the year 2022, allowing us to calculate the average annual rainfall amounts for each LAD. In addition, we examined the influence of topography by computing the average slope for each LAD. This calculation was based on a 90-meter resolution Digital Elevation Model (DEM) provided by Pope (2017).

Results and discussion

The analysis of the 2022 EDM data at the LAD level reveals a notable trend in CSO spill towards durations. This trend is characterized by a moderate to high skewness, with an adjusted Fisher-Pearson coefficient of 1.55, as illustrated in the histogram presented in Figure 1. In the box-plot, presence of outliers with exceptionally long spill durations reinforces this trend. These outliers are likely indicative of issues within the sewerage network, such as reduced hydraulic capacity due to blockages or potential inaccuracies in the EDM data caused by sensor malfunctions.

Figure 1. Histogram and box-plot of the average CSO spill durations in 2022.

The spatial autocorrelation analysis based on the Global Moran's I statistic indicates these durations are statistically significant clustered at both local and broader scales. Notably, within a 90 km distance band, the analysis identified the first peak in the z-score, approximately 21, and a corresponding p-value close to zero. This distance was selected as the most appropriate for the local analysis, aligning with recommended best practices outlined by ESRI (2023d) for fixed distance bands.

Using the identified 90 km distance band, the LISA analysis (Figure 2) revealed that LADs with longer CSO spill durations are mostly found in the western and northern regions, while those with shorter durations are in the eastern and southern regions. Moreover, the LISA cluster and significance maps highlights the presence of statistically significant spatial outliers. These outliers, shown in darker colours, may suggest LADs with notably different drainage system performance compared to neighbouring areas with similar climatic conditions and catchment characteristics. This indicates that local unidentified factors may have a significant impact on drainage network performance.

Figure 2. LISA cluster and significance map based on average CSO spill durations in 2022.

Further analysis using rainfall and topographical data revealed that these local patterns in CSO spill durations are correlated with environmental and geographical factors, as depicted in Figure 3. The scatter plots in this figure illustrate a clear trend: LADs with higher annual rainfall and steeper slopes tend to experience longer average annual CSO spill durations.

Figure 3. Relationship between CSO spill durations and environmental-economic factors.

Modern sewer systems are generally designed to align with local weather conditions, yet in the UK, many CSOs still in operation are legacies of infrastructure established prior to the 1980s. During that period, CSO structures were designed to limit the pass-forward flow to the Wastewater Treatment Plant (WWTP), typically set to six times the dry weather flow (Butler et al., 2018). The omission of rainfall considerations in older sewer systems may explain the observed patterns in the LISA cluster map, with longer CSO spill durations in regions with higher annual rainfall volumes, such as the western and northern areas in the UK. Moreover, these regions often face challenges posed by steeper terrain, which leads to faster runoff and higher net discharge per unit area. For example, in Wales, DEFRA (2015) has reported that overland flow from steep rural catchments contributes significantly to increased flood risks in urban areas. In contrast, the

flatter regions in the eastern and northeastern areas may also benefit from greater in-pipe storage capacity in combined sewers, as gravity pipes require minimal slope.

Nevertheless, these correlations remain relatively weak, suggesting the presence of additional local factors that influence CSO spill durations, and questioning whether CSO duration is a good way to quantify network performance. For instance, Giakoumis and Voulvoulis (2023) suggest that insufficient capacity at sewage treatment facilities contributes to increased CSO events. This is particularly evident when investigating spatial outliers in the LISA cluster map, where LADs of West Sussex demonstrate a clear pattern. In this area, despite ongoing new housing developments, most of the sewage treatment works near their maximum capacity. Consequently, illegal sewage discharges are becoming a common issue (Laville, 2022).

Conclusions and future work

Our spatial analysis of the EDM dataset for the year 2022 reveals that CSO spill patterns in England and Wales are influenced by regional climate and topography, suggesting inequities in sewer performance due to historical design practices. The presence of weak correlations and notable outliers underscores the need for further research into diverse potential influencing local factors, including sewer system hydraulic capacity, population growth, and investment in urban water infrastructure. An examination of these factors will provide a better understanding of the observed spatial patterns and help in developing targeted, effective strategies for sustainable CSO management, and looking for additional indicators of CSO performance.

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